

Improved Bonferroni mean operator to apprehend graph based data interconnections with application to the Hacker Attack system

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Abstract

The Bonferroni mean (BM) operator has extended the class of interrelationship handling fusion functions by modeling homogeneous pairwise interactions among data entities. This operator has been further extended to diverse directions with the intention of capturing dissimilar association that exists within data sets of different real-world systems like, social network systems, biological systems, etc. It has been observed that some of the existing forms of the BM operator pre-assumes a specific model of association among data entities during its formulation, which may not be feasible in many systems. In this study, an effort has been made to develop the framework of the BM operator by generalizing the structure of relationship patterns among data entities. Classical graphs are considered as a prominent tool of describing pairwise relations among data entities. Such consideration prompted the proposal of a systematized framework of an improved version of the BM operator, denoted by the f_G^{BM} operator, where the unconventional association among data entities are portrayed through different graphical patterns. The f_G^{BM} operator has been formulated in a way that the knowledge of interactional information depicted through graphs is embedded into its processing system with the aim of capturing precise interconnections among entities. The generalized variation of the f_G^{BM} operator has also been proposed by substituting the sub-components of the f_G^{BM} operator with other precise forms of the aggregation functions to provide an illustrative alignment, which is quite expressible and interpretable, and also facilitates modeling mandatory prerequisites of the decision systems. For an applicatory aspect, the proposed operators have been utilized over the Hacker attack system and have been presented with a numerical example. A detailed comprehensive analysis has been presented to demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed operators.

Keywords: Graphical structure, Aggregation operators, Bonferroni mean, Improved Bonferroni mean operator, Generalized Bonferroni mean operator, Hacker attack system

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1. Introduction

In the real-world, information has the position of centrality [1–3]. Accumulation of accessible information from the amalgamation of heterogeneous and homogeneous sources is the most prominent and emerging field of research in information sciences [4, 5]. One needs to gather all the available information concealed in the source data set to obtain an aggregated information such that the resultant information is the summarized representative of all the available unprocessed data. One of the robust tool that assists in information accumulation is the conceptualization of the aggregation operators [6, 7]. Such functions execute an important role in various processing and applicatory systems, such as data fusion [8–10], statistics [11], pattern recognition [12], social networks [13], etc. The most prominent class of aggregation operators are the averaging functions [14] and are extensively used in many real-life problems, like decision-making [15], image processing [16], etc. Nowadays, the class of averaging aggregation operators have been considerably upgraded to handle many advanced decision-making problems and to enhance the effectiveness of operator in handling association among different data inputs.

In many information accumulation frameworks, we encounter a situation where one desires to gather fragmented pieces of the available information in such a precise way that the intrinsic relationship pattern among those information sources is not deteriorated. For, instance if one wishes to obtain an accumulated opinion about a certain decision system from the individual opinions, it is mandatory to consider precise interconnections among those individuals (like in social networks [17]) to obtain genuine information model. Similarly, in multi-criteria decision making (*MCDM*) scenario [18], the alternatives are to be ranked based on the predefined criteria set, where criteria may involve different types of complex interconnections among them [19, 20]. The connection among data inputs have enhanced the efficiency of aggregation operators to model complex decision systems. If examples like mining and big data analysis are taken for reference [21, 22], then one of the available approaches by which the data input can be explicitly examined is the concept of the partition algorithm, where the databases are fragmented into different partition sets, and based on it, the aggregated representative data is obtained. Thus, the inclusion of association among data arguments while constructing the framework of aggregation operator is indispensable. One of the prominent relationship handling aggregation operators that can efficiently capture the pairwise homogeneous inter-connection among data entities is the Bonferroni mean (*BM*) [7, 23–25]. Some of the extensions of the *BM* operator are the partitioned Bonferroni mean (*PBM*) operator [26], extended Bonferroni mean (*EBM*) operator [27], extended partitioned Bonferroni mean (*EPBM*) operator [28], etc. The *PBM* operator handles interconnections among data inputs by assuming that inputs are fragmented into different partition sets. This operator assumes that inputs belonging to intra-partition sets are homogeneously associated to each other, while the inputs in inter-partition sets are not linked to each other. The *EBM* operator captures heterogeneous connections among data entities and is hence advantageous in modeling real-world decision problems. The *EPBM* operator takes into consideration partitioned structured heterogeneous relationships among data inputs. The above mentioned *BM*-type operators have also been utilized effectively over different fuzzy sets to handle association among imprecise and in-explicit data [29–33].

One of the prime concerns with each of the above mentioned extensions [26–28] of the BM operator is that they assume a rigid or pre-determined relationship structure among the inputs, and based on that structural information, the form of the aggregation operator has been formulated. In many applicatory systems, the structural inference of relationships among inputs may not be known to users in advance. So, it is quite complex to resolve which among the above mentioned forms of the BM operator is best suitable for the concerned decision-making problem. For example, in the commercial world, there is an overabundance of information related to different products supplied by online stores. This results in inefficiency of customers to search desired product because of huge amount of information available which may be sometimes irrelevant to a specific user or customer. It is admissible that the opinion of a customer may highly get influenced by the recommendations or ratings provided by their neighboring users like mutual friends, relatives, etc. The network of neighboring users portraying connections among them can be easily availed through social media platforms, and based on their respective opinions or ratings, the aggregated rating of the product may be obtained. It is noteworthy that the aggregated rating value highly depends on the connections among different group of individuals as they may have different tastes. Since, there is no specified form of relationship structure among the users, hence, it is difficult to determine which of the above mentioned forms of BM extensions is worth suitable for such problems. To handle the stated issue, it is desirable to utilize a mathematical tool that can describe unconventional associations among data inputs. Also, such characterization of interrelationships needs to be embedded into the aggregation process for an effective fusion of information.

For an effectual description of the pairwise interrelationship pattern among the data sources or entities, we consider the classical graphs, generally taken as simple graphs [34]. We assume that the connections among different entities are depicted through a graph G with the vertex set $V(G)$ describing the available entities, and the edge set $E(G)$ represents pairwise interconnections among those entities. In the proposed study, different structure of interrelationship patterns among entities are described via different patterns of graphs. For instance, a complete graph represents homogeneous interconnections among entities, whereas graphs with different components represent the partitioned structured relationship among the entities. The unconventional interrelationships that exists among different data entities can be captured effectively through different graphical patterns, thus enables to describe vivid models of real- world problems. Our study focuses on formulation of a mathematical framework of an upgraded form of the different interrelationships structure based extension of BM operator in a way that the information of interrelationship structure among different entities are portrayed through different graphical patterns. With deep insight, such an improved form of the BM operator has been proposed and is denoted by the f_G^{BM} operator. The proposed aggregation operator is much more genuine and sustainable in handling connections among entities as compared to the other mentioned forms of the BM operator, like PBM , EBM , $EPBM$. The reason is that the proposed operator takes connective information among entities through generalized graphical patterns, whereas the other mentioned operators pre-assume that the pattern of relationships among entities are readily available to users in advance, thus, assuring the flexibility of the proposed f_G^{BM} operator. In precise, the

proposed study aims at the following points:

- Representation of interrelationship information among entities through graphs.
- Analyzing vivid heterogeneous and homogeneous connections that exist in real-world situation through different graphical patterns.
- Propose a framework of BM-type aggregation operator by considering the generalized relationship pattern among entities. This proposed framework processes the relationship among inputs based on graphs.

One of the most disregarded issues while framing the structure of the aggregation operator for utilization in many real-world systems is the effectiveness of the operator in modeling genuine decision scenarios. The aggregation operators should be effective in handling specific mandatory requirements as described by the decision systems along with the apprehension of exact interconnections among different entities [7]. Therefore, it is important to formulate a suitable form of aggregation operators that can facilitate mandatory prerequisites described by the system in an environment where the interconnections among entities are portrayed through graphs. In this regard, an explicit form of the BM operator has been proposed by suitably restoring the components of the proposed f_G^{BM} operator with other conjunctive and the averaging aggregation functions. Such variation in the sub-components of the proposed f_G^{BM} operator leads to evolving of the generalized form of the f_G^{BM} operator, denoted by f_G^* . The advantages of proposing the generalized form of the f_G^{BM} operator can be expressible through the following points:

- First, it captures interrelationship information among different entities depicted through graphs, hence flexible in handling precise associations among different entities.
- Through the generalized form, different mandatory requisites can be established over different sub-components of the f_G^{BM} operator to get the preferred satisfaction degree, and thus effective in describing the exact requirements of the decision systems.
- The generalized operator makes us accessible a wide range of representations of the proposed f_G^{BM} operator by taking variations in the mandatory conditions, thus can be applied over vivid real-world systems.
- The generalized f_G^{BM} operator can be fragmented into manageable sub-parts, and the properties of these sub-parts can be accumulated together to obtain the cumulative property of the generalized form. Thus, significant properties of the proposed operator like commutativity, and its behavioral pattern can be recognized effortlessly by its generalized form.

The structural framework of the proposed study is outlined as follows. In section 2, the basic concepts and definitions of aggregation operators, particularly the BM operator and its extensions has been discussed. Section 3 focuses on proposing a few notions that would facilitate portraying relationships among different entities by utilizing different graphs. In section 4, dissimilar interrelationship patterns that exist among the entities are

described through different graphical structures. Section 5 focuses on proposing the f_{BM}^G operator and its weighted version. In section 6, the proposed f_{BM}^G operator has been further remodeled by generalizing it in such a way that it is effective in handling mandatory prerequisites of the considered system. Section 7 provides an illustrative numerical example of the Hacker attack system to demonstrate the working efficiency of the proposed operators. At last, section 8 provides some concluding remarks along with the future extent of this work.

2. Basic preliminaries and review of BM variants

In this section, we briefly recall the key concepts of aggregation functions and review the different variants of BM operator.

2.1. Aggregation operators

Definition 1. [35, 36] *An aggregation operator defined over the set $[0, 1]^n$ is a function $f : [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$ that satisfies the underlying properties:*

1. *f fulfils the boundary conditions, i.e. we have $f(0, \dots, 0) = 0$ and $f(1, \dots, 1) = 1$;*
2. *f is non-decreasing in each of its arguments.*

Here, n represents the number of entities based on which the summarized aggregated information has to be obtained. Depending on the behavioral pattern of the aggregation operators with respect to the concerned input arguments, they can be sub-classified broadly into the following categories.

Definition 2. [35] *An aggregation operator $f : [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$ is mentioned as*

- *Averaging, if it satisfies $\min(Y) \leq f(Y) \leq \max(Y)$, for all $Y \in [0, 1]^n$;*
- *Conjunctive, if it fulfils the condition $f(Y) \leq \min(Y)$, for all $Y \in [0, 1]^n$;*
- *Disjunctive, if it fulfils the condition $f(Y) \geq \max(Y)$, for all $Y \in [0, 1]^n$.*
- *The aggregation functions which could not be classified in the above mentioned subcategories are said to be mixed aggregation operators.*

The conjunctive and disjunctive aggregation functions are utilized in modeling logical *AND*, *OR* connectives, respectively. The typical examples of the conjunctive operators (disjunctive operators) are t-norms (t-conorms) [7, 37] defined over $[0, 1]^2$.

Definition 3. [35] *The aggregation operator $f : [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$ is said to be*

- *idempotent if it satisfies $f(y, \dots, y) = y$, for all $y \in [0, 1]$;*

- commutative if for any permutation $\sigma : \{1, \dots, n\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, n\}$, we have $f(y_1, \dots, y_n) = f(y_{\sigma(1)}, \dots, y_{\sigma(n)})$ for every $(y_1, \dots, y_n) \in [0, 1]^n$.

Because of the non-decreasing property satisfied by the aggregation operators, the averaging behavior and idempotency property are equivalent.

It is frequent to work with a family of operators with $n = 2, 3, \dots$ number of input arguments that satisfy the underlying properties of the aggregation operator. The extended aggregation operators are used on such grounds that grasp any number of input arguments.

Definition 4. [35, 38] An extended aggregation operator over $\cup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [0, 1]^n$ is a function $\tilde{f} : \cup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$ (\mathbb{N} denotes set of natural numbers) that fulfils the underlying properties:

1. \tilde{f} confined or restricted over the set $[0, 1]^n$ is an aggregation operator for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.
2. for the case of $n = 1$, \tilde{f} is an identity function.

Some of the prominent examples of the extended aggregation functions are the arithmetic mean operator, geometric mean operator, t-norms and t-conorms (due to the associativity of t-norms and t-conorms, their extensions over $[0, 1]^n$ is well defined) [24, 35].

2.2. BM and its variants

The *BM* operator was first introduced by Bonferroni in 1950 [23]. Later, Beliakov et al. [24, p. 63] redefined it as summing the product pairs raised to a power, and is expressed through the following equation.

Definition 5. [24, p. 63] With the assumption that $p, q \geq 0$ and $p + q > 0$, the *BM* operator over $[0, 1]^n$ is a mapping $BM : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$, and is given by:

$$BM(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) = \left(\frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i,j=1, j \neq i}^n y_i^p y_j^q \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}}.$$

Yager [25] interpreted *BM* operator as a kind of combined **anding** and **averaging** operator by re-framing it as follows:

$$BM(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^p \left(\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{\substack{j \neq i \\ j=1}}^n y_j^q \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}}.$$

The conceptualization of the generalized *BM* operator was proposed in [7] by substituting each components utilized in the *BM* operator by other conjunctive, disjunctive or mean-type aggregation operators. The definition of the generalized form of the *BM* operator is stated as follows.

Definition 6. [7] Let $\bar{M} = \langle M_1, M_2, C \rangle$ comprises of three-tuple functions, where $M_1 : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $M_2 : [0, 1]^{n-1} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $C : [0, 1]^2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are the aggregation operators such that the operator C possess continuous strictly monotone diagonal, denoted by δ_C , defined as $\delta_C(t) = C(t, t) \forall t \in [0, 1]$. Let the inverse diagonal of C is denoted by δ_C^{-1} . Then the generalized BM operator, denoted by $B_{\bar{M}}$ is given by the following form:

$$B_{\bar{M}}(y) = \delta_C^{-1}(M_1(C(y_1, M_2(y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n)), \dots, C(y_n, M_2(y_1, \dots, y_{n-1}))))$$

The aggregation operators utilized in the $B_{\bar{M}}$ which are M_1 , M_2 , and C , respectively generalize the arithmetic mean, power mean with power q and the product operation, respectively in the traditional form of the BM operator. This generalized form was proposed by Beliakov et al. in [7] and is beneficial in specifying the desired number of mandatory requisites in the decision systems. It is noteworthy that in this generalization of the BM operator, the semantic structure of the interrelationship among the inputs is not altered.

Let us assume that $\mathbf{C} = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ be the source or input set, and let (y_1, \dots, y_n) be the input argument related to the source set \mathbf{C} . Dutta et al. [27] described such homogeneous connection among the input set \mathbf{C} through the hierarchical relationship structure as described in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Representation of the homogeneous relationship among inputs

Further, an argument has been made that the relationship among the inputs could be heterogeneous in nature. Such a relationship pattern among inputs lead to the proposition of the EBM operator [27]. The heterogeneous relationship among the inputs refer that the source set \mathbf{C} comprises both the dependent and independent inputs. The set \mathbf{C} is divided into two disjoint subsets C' and D , where each input C_{h_i} in C' is heterogeneously interlinked to some non-empty subset B_{h_i} of inputs in $C' - \{C_{h_i}\}$, while D comprises independent inputs. For each $C_{h_i} \in C'$, let I_i be the index set of B_{h_i} , and let I' be the index set of D . It can be noted that if D is an empty set and all inputs in C' are homogeneously related to each other then one may avail the form of the BM operator as stated by Yager [25]. The connection among inputs of \mathbf{C} in the framework of the EBM operator can be depicted through Fig. 2. Based on this connective information, the EBM operator is defined as follows.

Definition 7. [29] With the assumption that $p, q \geq 0$ and $p + q > 0$, the EBM operator over $[0, 1]^n$ is a mapping $EBM: [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$, and is given by:

$$EBM(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) = \left(\frac{n - |I'|}{n} \left(\frac{1}{n - |I'|} \sum_{i \notin I'} y_i^p \left(\frac{1}{|I_i|} \sum_{j \in I_i} y_j^q \right) \right)^{\frac{p}{p+q}} + \frac{|I'|}{n} \left(\frac{1}{|I'|} \sum_{i \in I'} y_i^p \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (1)$$

with the convention that $\frac{0}{0} = 1$, where $|I_i|$ and $|I'|$ denote the cardinality of the sets I_i and I' , respectively.

Figure 2: Representation of the heterogeneous relationship

Another eminent extension of the BM operator is the *PBM* operator [26]. This form of the BM operator is based on the assumption that the source set \mathbf{C} is sub-divided into mutually disjoint partition sets P_1, \dots, P_d with the cardinality of each partition set greater than equal to two. For any partition set P_h , and for every input $C_{h_i} \in P_h$, C_{h_i} is homogeneously interlinked to all the inputs in $P_h - \{C_{h_i}\}$. Also, no interrelationship exists between pair of inputs belonging to two different partition sets. This kind of interrelationship pattern can be represented through Fig. 3, and based on that representation, *PBM* operator is defined as follows:

Definition 8. (Partitioned Bonferroni Mean (PBM)) [26] *With the assumption that $p, q \geq 0$ and $p+q > 0$, the PBM operator over $[0, 1]^n$ is a mapping $PBM: [0, 1]^n \rightarrow [0, 1]$, and is given by:*

$$PBM(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) = \frac{1}{d} \left(\sum_{h=1}^d \left(\frac{1}{|P_h|} \sum_{i \in P_h} y_i^p \left(\frac{1}{|P_h| - 1} \sum_{\substack{j \neq i \\ j \in P_h}} y_j^q \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \right) \right) \quad (2)$$

with the convention that $\frac{0}{0} = 1$, where the input set \mathbf{C} is subdivided into mutually disjoint partition sets P_1, \dots, P_d , and the cardinality of each partition set P_h is denoted by $|P_h|$ for every $h = 1, \dots, d$.

Figure 3: Representation of the partition structure relationship

One can observe that different semantic structures of the interrelation pattern while fusing the data information has led to different forms of the BM operator. Further, we need to provide the explicitly defined interrelationship pattern among inputs while doing the aggregation process to find the exact form of operator. These facts raise the concerns that how we could effectively describe and characterize such semantic structure of the interrelationship patterns in a generic way and surpass it in the aggregation process to fix the exact form of operator.

In practice, one can easily identify such a relationship structure among the data sources in many physical

Figure 4: Description of different types of interconnections among data inputs that is described via hierarchical diagrams in Figures 1-3 which is illustrated via graphs.

systems, such as in the social network system and the sensory network system. In such systems, the connection among sources are effectively modeled through graphs and that realization works as an intuition to model semantic structure of the interrelationships among inputs in BM operator via graphs as described in Figure 4. Further, graph provides an efficient data structure that can easily surpass in the aggregation process along with inputs while configuring the operator.

Based on the above analysis, we initiate our work by first describing the interrelationship patterns that exist within the data sources before aggregating them through the mechanism of classical graphs as they are effective in portraying pairwise relations among data inputs.

3. Characterization of interrelationship pattern through graphs

Oftentimes, we confront the information fusion scenarios, where we not only need to amalgamate fragmented pieces of available information but also try to capture the underlying interrelationships that exist among the information sources while executing the aggregation process to make a reliable information fusion model. For example, when one attempts to form a group overall opinion about a certain topic from the individual opinions, it may be important to consider the underlying interrelationship structure (like a social network) among these individuals. Similarly, when we fuse information from a sensory network system, the underlying network that

describes the interaction among the sensors needs to be taken into consideration in the process of gathering summarized information. Such interrelationships about underlying information sources are also common in the *MCDM* context, where criteria might have connections and that should be captured during the evaluation of the overall performance of alternatives under these criteria.

An initiatory step of seizing out such underlying interrelationship patterns among the information sources is the formation of the mathematical model that can formally describe such connections among objects or entities. Further, the framework of characterizing different interrelationship pattern among entities and intermingling it into the process of information accumulation while aggregating it is pivotal to design so that some knowledge can be extracted from the encapsulated information. To mathematically formalize the connections among information sources, we adopt here the concept of classical graphs, which is prominent machinery for describing pairwise relations among the objects or the entities.

Graphs can be considered as an effectual tool of portraying connections among different entities. One can relate the vertices of the graph G with the available entities, and the connectivity or underlying interrelationship among those entities can be described through the edges of the considered graph. For instance, consider the graph G with vertex set $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5\}$ and the edge set $E(G) = \{v_1v_3, v_3v_5, v_3v_4\}$. The set $V(G)$ can be considered as the available entities, and the set $E(G)$ represents that the entity v_1 is connected to v_3 , v_3 is connected to v_5 , and v_3 is also connected to v_4 . Furthermore, no other connections among entities in $V(G)$ exist except those described in $E(G)$. It is assumed that the graphs are simple graphs, i.e. it has no parallel edge nor any loops. We initiate the work by providing a few definitions that assist in describing the interconnections among entities. We consider the graph G with the vertex set $V(G)$ and the edge set $E(G)$.

Definition 9. *Two entities $v_i, v_j \in V(G)$ are said to be directly dependent on each other if the two vertices are adjacent in the graph, i.e. $v_iv_j \in E(G)$. If v_i and v_j are directly dependent entities, then it can be symbolized by $v_i \sim v_j$.*

The degree of an entity $v_i \in V(G)$ denotes the number of entities which are directly dependent on v_i . Define the set $[[v_i]] = \{v_j : v_i \sim v_j\}$, then $[[v_i]]$ is the set of all those entities in $V(G)$ which are directly dependent on the entity v_i .

Definition 10. *Two entities $v_i, v_j \in V(G)$ are said to be indirectly dependent on each other if there exists a finite sequence of entities, say v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k ($k \geq 1$) such that $v_i \sim v_1, v_1 \sim v_2, \dots, v_k \sim v_j$.*

Graphically, indirectly dependent entities can be described by the availability of a path between those considered vertices in the graph G .

Definition 11. *The entity $v_i \in V(G)$ is said to be totally independent if there does not exist any entity say v_j such that $v_i \sim v_j$. Graphically, the totally independent entities are those vertices v_i in G such that there is no edge which is incident to the vertex v_i .*

Example 3.1. Consider a graph G with vertex set $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5\}$, and edge set $E(G) = \{v_1v_2, v_2v_3, v_3v_4\}$. Then, $v_1 \sim v_2$, $v_2 \sim v_3$, and $v_3 \sim v_4$. But, v_1 and v_4 are indirectly dependent; v_5 is a totally independent entity.

Directly dependent, indirectly dependent, and totally independent entities portrayed through graphs are convenient in describing many physical world phenomena. For instance, Google maps are widely used to describe the transportation system between two destination points. The destination points may be considered as the vertices and an edge exists between two destination points if there is a roadway connecting them. Two destination points are directly dependent if they can be adjoined through a roadway; they are said to be indirectly dependent if one needs to follow a series of roadways to reach it out.

Another example is the situation of the battlefield, where vertices represent different combat units/ departments consisting of army men; two units are directly dependent if they coordinate with each other, where the coordination depends on the nonrestrictive communication between them. The two units are said to be indirectly dependent if the respective coordination between them depends on other units because of the complex communication system.

Remark 3.1. It is noteworthy that \sim relation over the entity set $V(G)$ is irreflexive (as there is no loops in the graph), symmetric, but need not be transitive; while the relation of 'indirectly dependent' between two entities is symmetric, transitive, but need not be reflexive.

We now formalize some of the core concepts associated with the graph in terms of relations between entities. It forms the basis of the characterization of the entity relationship.

Definition 12. Let $V(G) = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ be the set of entities, then the set $V(G)$ is said to be:

1. Complete, if every pair of entities are directly dependent on each other;
2. Connected, if every pair of entities is either directly dependent or indirectly dependent on each other.

Graphically, a complete set $V(G)$ can be visualized through a complete graph and the connected set $V(G)$ can be depicted through a connected graph G .

Definition 13. Let $V(G)$ be the set of entities. A non-empty subset P of $V(G)$ is said to be maximal connected subset if the following conditions hold:

- The set P is connected set;
- If P_1 is another connected set contained in $V(G)$, then either $P_1 \subset P$ or $P_1 \cap P = \emptyset$.

Graphically, the maximal connected sets can be visualized through the components of the graph G .

Remark 3.2. It can be noted that the maximal connected subsets splits up the entity set into mutually disjoint subsets say P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d such that $\cup_{h=1}^d P_h = V(G)$.

Next, we consider the relational matrix corresponding to the relation ' \sim ' defined over the entity set $V(G)$. We construct an $(n \times n)$ matrix $A = (A_{ij})_{(n \times n)}$ as follows:

$$A_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{iff } v_i \sim v_j, i \neq j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The relational matrix is used to describe the interrelationship pattern among entities through a compact matrix representation.

Remark 3.3. *It is noteworthy that the relational matrix A is formulated based on the interrelationship patterns that exist among the entities. The subsequent aim of the proposed work is to develop the framework of the Bonferroni mean operator based on the interrelationships expressed through graphical networks. In the construction procedure of the Bonferroni mean operator, we are much interested in knowing whether two different entities are interlinked to each other or not; the relationship between the same entity (i.e., reflexive behavior of the relation ' \sim ' that describes the directly dependent relation among entities) are never considered. Thus, in A , the diagonal elements are taken as zero to express the consideration that we are not interested in modeling the reflexive behavior of the relation ' \sim '.*

Next we provide a proposition that enables us to characterize existence of totally independent entity among the set of entities $V(G)$.

Proposition 3.1. (Characterization of totally independent entities) *The following statements characterize existence of a totally independent entity in the set $V(G)$:*

- $[[v_i]] = \emptyset$, for some $v_i \in V(G)$;
- There exist a row or column in the relational matrix A with all zero entries;
- The graphical representation has a vertex say v_i such that no edge is incident to it.

Remark 3.4. *If there exists a totally independent entity in the set $V(G)$, then the corresponding relational matrix has a zero eigenvalue. But, converse need not be true. For example, consider the set $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ and the edge set $E(G) = \{v_1v_3, v_2v_3\}$. Then the corresponding relational matrix A is not invertible, hence zero is the eigenvalue of the matrix, but there does not exist any totally independent entity. All the entities in $V(G)$ are either directly dependent or indirectly independent on each other.*

Next, we proceed towards describing different type of interrelationship pattern that exists among entities through different graphical structures.

4. Apprehending interrelationship pattern among entities via different structures of graphs

In the real world physical phenomena, different types of relationships may exist among entities. For instance, in the case of *MCDM* context, attributes may be homogeneously or heterogeneously related to each other. This

section aims at rendering different connections among entities through a vivid graphical structure which will be surpassed in the procedure of information accumulation to get the knowledgeable encapsulated information.

Definition 14. Let $V(G) = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ be the set of entities. The relationship among entities is said to be:

- *independent if all the entities $v_i \in V(G)$ are totally independent;*
- *homogeneous if all the entities are directly dependent on rest of the entities;*
- *heterogeneous if the entity $v_i \in V(G)$ is directly dependent on some subset of entities $B_i \subset V(G) - \{v_i\}$. (Note that in this case there may exist some entity, say v_j such that the corresponding B_j is an empty set. Then, that v_j can be considered as the totally independent entity.)*
- *homogeneously partitioned if the entities are divided into mutually disjoint partition sets P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d with $|P_h| \geq 2$, $\cup_{h=1}^d P_h = V(G)$, such that if $v_i \in P_h$ for some $h \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, then it is directly dependent on rest of the entities in P_h ; while the entities of inter-partition are neither directly nor indirectly dependent on each other.*
- *heterogeneously partitioned if the entities are divided into mutually disjoint partition sets, say P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d , with $|P_h| \geq 2$, $\cup_{h=1}^d P_h = V(G)$, in the sense that $\forall v_i \in P_h$, there exists a non-empty subset B_i^h of $P_h - \{v_i\}$ such that v_i is directly dependent on all of the entities in B_i^h . Furthermore, entities belonging to two different partition sets are neither directly nor indirectly dependent on each other.*

Next we present some propositions that assists in identifying mentioned interrelationship patterns among entities.

Proposition 4.1. *The following statements are equivalent and characterizes independent relationship among entities:*

- *All the entities $v_i \in V(G)$ are totally independent;*
- *$[[v_i]] = \emptyset$ for all $v_i \in V(G)$;*
- *the graphical representation of the entities in set $V(G)$ has $E(G)$ as an empty set;*
- *the relational matrix is a null matrix.*

Proposition 4.2. *The following statements are equivalent and characterizes homogeneous relationship among entities:*

- *All the entities $v_i \in V(G)$ are directly dependent on the rest of the entities;*
- *$[[[v_i]]] = |V(G)| - 1$ for all $v_i \in V(G)$, where $[[[v_i]]]$ represents cardinality of the set $[[v_i]]$;*
- *the graphical representation of the entities in set $V(G)$ is a complete graph;*

- the relational matrix has all non-diagonal elements as 1.

It can be noted that every complete graph represents homogeneous interrelationship among entities.

Proposition 4.3. *The following statements are equivalent and characterizes heterogeneous relationship among entities:*

- For any entity $v_i \in V(G)$ there exists some subset $B_i \subset V(G) - \{v_i\}$ such that v_i is directly dependent on all the entities in B_i (here B_i can be empty set too);
- the set $V(G)$ has maximal connected subsets say P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d , with $|P_h| \geq 1$ for all $h = 1, \dots, d$, and it has at least one maximal connected subset with cardinality greater than equal to two;
- the graphical representation of the entities in $V(G)$ has components, say P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d , with $|P_h| \geq 1$ for all $h = 1, \dots, d$, and the graph has at least one component with cardinality greater than equal to two;
- $[[v_i]] = \emptyset$ if $v_i \in P_h, |P_h| = 1$; else $1 \leq |[v_i]| \leq |P_h| - 1$ if $v_i \in P_h$ and $|P_h| \geq 2$;
- the relational matrix is of the form of block diagonal matrix, where matrices in diagonal are either zero matrices of order 1, or a square symmetric matrix of order greater than equal to two, with at least one entry in a row (or a column) as 1.

Proposition 4.4. *The following statements are equivalent and characterizes homogeneously partitioned relationship among entities:*

- the entities are divided into mutually disjoint partition sets P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d with $|P_h| \geq 2, \cup_{h=1}^d P_h = V(G)$ in the sense that entity v_i belonging to a particular partition set say P_h is directly dependent on rest of the entities in that partition set, i.e. $P_h - \{v_i\}$; while the entities belonging to inter-partition are neither directly nor indirectly dependent on each other;
- the set $V(G)$ has d number of maximal connected subsets P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d , with $|P_h| \geq 2, \cup_{h=1}^d P_h = V(G)$. Also, each entity in a particular partition set, say P_h is directly dependent on rest of the entities in P_h , and entities belonging to different partition sets are neither directly nor indirectly related to each other;
- $[[v_i]] = |P_h| - 1$ for every $v_i \in P_h$ for all $h = 1, \dots, d$;
- the graphical representation of the set $V(G)$ is the disconnected graph with d number of components, and cardinality of each component is greater than equals two. Furthermore, each component is itself a complete subgraph;
- the relational matrix is the block diagonal matrix, with diagonal matrices as square matrix of order greater than equal to two. Entries of each diagonal matrices have non-diagonal entries as 1.

Proposition 4.5. *The following statements are equivalent and characterizes heterogeneously partitioned relationship among entities:*

- *the entities are divided into mutually disjoint partition sets P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d , with $|P_h| \geq 2$, $\cup_{h=1}^d P_h = V(G)$, in the sense that for all $v_i \in P_h$, there exists a non-empty subset $B_i^h \subset P_h - \{v_i\}$ such that v_i is directly dependent on all of the entities in B_i^h . Furthermore, entities belonging to two different partition sets are neither directly nor indirectly dependent on each other;*
- *the set $V(G)$ has d number of maximal connected subsets P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d , with $|P_h| \geq 2$, $\cup_{h=1}^d P_h = V(G)$;*
- *$1 \leq |[v_i]| \leq |P_h| - 1$ for every $v_i \in P_h$ and for all $h = 1, \dots, d$;*
- *the graphical representation of the set $V(G)$ is the disconnected graph with d number of components with cardinality of each component is greater than equals two;*
- *the relational matrix is a block diagonal matrix, with diagonal matrices as square symmetric matrices of order greater than equal to two. These diagonal matrices have at least one entry in a row (or column) as 1.*

Example 4.1. *We provide a set of examples to demonstrate the relational matrix structure according to the above illustrated propositions as follows:*

- *If $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$ and $E(G) = \{v_1v_2, v_3v_4, v_4v_5\}$, the graph has total three components, each of order 1, 2, 3, respectively. The relational matrix is given by:*

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Here, the relational matrix A is a block diagonal matrix with three diagonal matrices, a zero matrix of order 1, square symmetric matrices of order two and three respectively, with at least one entry in a row (or a column) as 1. Thus, the graph depicts a heterogeneous relationship among entities.

- *If $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5\}$ and $E(G) = \{v_1v_2, v_3v_4, v_4v_5, v_3v_5\}$, the graph has total two components, each*

of order 2, 3, respectively. The relational matrix is given by:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

It is a block diagonal matrix with diagonal matrices as square symmetric matrices of order two and three with the non-diagonal entries of each matrix as 1. Thus, depicts a homogeneously partitioned relationship among entities.

- If $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$ and $E(G) = \{v_1v_2, v_3v_4, v_4v_5, v_5v_6\}$, the graph has total two components each of order 2, 4 respectively. The relational matrix is given by:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The relational matrix is a block diagonal matrix with diagonal matrices are square symmetric matrices of order two and four respectively and these matrices have at least one entry in a row (or a column) as 1. Thus, depicts a heterogeneously partitioned relationship among entities.

The above propositions enable us to express different connections among entities that arise in many physical systems through different graph patterns. Now the information portrayed through graphs has to be encompassed into the mechanism of the aggregation procedure to get the encapsulated information. For proposing such a framework, we proceed towards the subsequent section.

5. Improved Bonferroni mean aggregation operator over generalized structures of graph

From section 4, it is quite apparent that the pairwise connections among different entities can be prominently portrayed through the structures of graphs. It has been manifested that vivid interrelationship patterns that may exists within entities, like in social networks, sensory networks, battlefield networks, etc. can be effortlessly customized through different graphical patterns. The principal aim of this work is to establish an information fusion model in a more precise way where interconnections among entities are depicted through graphs and this information can be be surpassed into the aggregation mechanism so that an encapsulated knowledgeable

information can be obtained. The frameworks of the *BM* operator as discussed before presumes a particular configuration of interconnections. In this section, an effort has been made to remodel the framework of *BM* operator in a way that the connection among entities are depicted through graphs, which is effortlessly available to users, like in social networks, sensory networks, etc.

Let G be a graph with the vertex set $V(G) = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ and the edge set $E(G)$. Then, $V(G)$ can be considered as the set of available entities and edges depict pairwise interconnections among those entities. We assume that the graph G has d number of components P_1, P_2, \dots, P_d , with $|P_h| \geq 1$, for all $h = 1, \dots, d$. Without loss of generality, one may assume that P_1, \dots, P_r are components with cardinality greater than equal to two, and the rest are of cardinality one. Denote the neighborhood of the vertex v_i by $N(v_i)$ and is given as $N(v_i) = \{v_j : v_i v_j \in E(G)\}$. Since we are considering only undirected edges so if $v_j \in N(v_i)$ then we certainly have $v_i \in N(v_j)$. Let $g(v_i) \in [0, 1]$ denotes the opinion value corresponding to the vertex or entity $v_i \in V(G)$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$. With these assumptions, we proceed towards defining improved Bonferroni mean aggregation operator over the generalized patterns of graph.

Definition 15. Let G be a graph with the vertex set $V(G) = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ and the edge set $E(G)$. Let $g(v_i)$ denotes the opinion value corresponding to the vertex $v_i \in V(G)$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$. The improved Bonferroni mean aggregation operator over the graph G , denoted by f_G^{BM} , where $f_G^{BM} : [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$ is defined as follows:

$$f_G^{BM}(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) = \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{h=1}^r \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h}{|V(G)|} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{r} \left[\sum_{h=1}^r \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{v_i \in P_h} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \right] \right\}^p + \left(\frac{\sum_{h \notin \{1, \dots, r\}} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h}{|V(G)|} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{h \notin \{1, \dots, r\}} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ |P_h|=1}} (g(v_i))^p \right\}^{\frac{1}{p}} \right]^p \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } v_i \in P_h \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$p, q \geq 0$ with $p + q > 0$ and $|V(G)|, |N(v_i)|, |P_h|$ denote cardinality of the sets $V(G), N(v_i), P_h$, respectively.

The equation 4 is interpreted as follows. It has been assumed that the graph G has components P_1, \dots, P_d , where P_1, \dots, P_r are the components with cardinality greater than equal to two and the rest of the components are of cardinality one. The components of cardinality one can be considered as totally independent entities. The expression $\left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{\substack{v_i \in V(G) \\ h \notin \{1, \dots, r\}}} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ |P_h|=1}} (g(v_i))^p \right\}$ represent the encapsulated opinion value obtained from all the totally independent entities. On considering the set P_h , where $h \in \{1, \dots, r\}$, if $v_i \in P_h$ then we certainly have $|N(v_i)| > 0$. The expression $\left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{v_i \in P_h} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}}$ denotes the satisfaction level obtained from the component P_h of the graph G . Then, the expression $\left\{ \frac{1}{r} \left[\sum_{h=1}^r \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{v_i \in P_h} (g(v_i))^p \right\} \right] \right\}^p$

$\left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \Bigg\}$ evaluates the average satisfaction level obtained from all the components with cardinality greater than equal to two, i.e the aggregated satisfaction level obtained from the components P_1, \dots, P_r . Finally, the aggregated value obtained from all the components P_1, \dots, P_d of the graph G is obtained through equation 4 by utilizing p^{th} -power arithmetic mean operator.

Remark 5.1. We point out some of the special cases as follows:

1. When all the entities are homogeneously connected to each other, i.e. the graph is a complete graph, then equation 4 looks alike the BM operator and is given by the following form:

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{|V(G)|} \sum_{v_i \in V(G)} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|V(G)| - 1} \sum_{\substack{v_j \in V(G) \\ j \neq i}} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \quad (5)$$

2. When the entities are homogeneously partitioned, then the corresponding graph G has components with cardinality of each greater than equal to two. Furthermore, all the components are complete subgraph. Then equation 4 reduces to the following form:

$$\frac{1}{r} \left[\sum_{h=1}^r \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{v_i \in P_h} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|P_h| - 1} \sum_{\substack{v_j \in P_h \\ j \neq i}} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \right] \quad (6)$$

One can visualize that the structure of this operator looks alike the PBM operator.

3. When the entities are heterogeneously partitioned, i.e. there are only r components in G namely P_1, P_2, \dots, P_r with cardinality of each greater than equal to two. Then the equation 4 reduces to the following form:

$$\frac{1}{r} \left[\sum_{h=1}^r \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{v_i \in P_h} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \right] \quad (7)$$

4. When there is only one connected component P_1 in the graph G with cardinality greater than equal to two ($r = 1$), and the remaining components are of cardinality one, then equation 4 reduces to the following form:

$$\left(\frac{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^1}{|V(G)|} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^1} \sum_{v_i \in P_1} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{p}{p+q}} + \frac{|V(G)| - \sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^1}{|V(G)|} \left(\frac{1}{|V(G)| - \sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^1} \sum_{\substack{v_i \in V(G) \\ |N(v_i)|=0}} (g(v_i))^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (8)$$

This operator looks alike the EBM operator.

5. When all the entities are independent, then the corresponding graph consists of the vertex set $V(G)$ with an

empty edge set. In such case equation 4 reduces to the following form:

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{|V(G)|} \sum_{v_i \in V(G)} (g(v_i))^p \right\}^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (9)$$

Thus we obtain p^{th} -power arithmetic mean operator.

6. When the graph is k -regular connected graph then we get the following form of equation 4:

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{|V(G)|} \sum_{v_i \in V(G)} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{k} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \quad (10)$$

Nowadays, Bipartite graphs are extensively utilized in many field of physical phenomenon. For instance, in the complex biological systems, Bipartite graphs are used widely in medicine and network biology [39]. Such graphs are also used in the field of cloud computing as well [40]. We present the conceptualization of Bipartite relationship among entities, and provide a mechanism of aggregating information when connections among entities are given in the form of Bipartite graphs.

Definition 16. Let $V(G) = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ ($n \geq 2$) be the set of entities. Then entities are said to follow a Bipartite relationship if the set $V(G)$ can be subdivided into two mutually disjoint non-empty subsets of vertices D_1, D_2 such that $D_1 \cup D_2 = V(G)$, and for each entity $v_i \in D_1$, there exists a set $B_i^2 \subset D_2$ such that v_i is directly dependent on each entity of B_i^2 . Similarly, for each entity $v_j \in D_2$, there exists a set $B_j^1 \subset D_1$ such that v_j is directly dependent on each entity of B_j^1 . Graphically, a bipartite relation among entities can be visualized through a bipartite graph.

Then entities are said to follow complete bipartite relationship if the set $V(G)$ can be subdivided into two mutually disjoint non-empty subsets D_1, D_2 such that $D_1 \cup D_2 = V(G)$, and each entity $v_i \in D_1$ is directly dependent on each entity of D_2 . Similarly, each entity $v_j \in D_2$ is directly dependent on each entity of D_1 . Graphically, a complete bipartite relation among entities can be visualized through a complete bipartite graph.

Remark 5.2. Depending on the Bipartite relationship pattern, the relational matrix can be characterized as follows:

1. If the entities follow Bipartite relation, then we have $0 \leq |[v_i]| \leq |D_2|$ if $v_i \in D_1$ ($0 \leq |[v_j]| \leq |D_1|$ if $v_j \in D_2$). Also, the relational matrix is the square symmetric matrix such that the row or column corresponding to each $v_i \in D_1$ ($v_j \in D_2$) is of either zero entries, or the maximum number of ones in that row or column is at the most cardinality of D_2 (cardinality of D_1).
2. If the entities follow complete Bipartite relationship, then $[v_i] = |D_2|$ if $v_i \in D_1$ ($[v_j] = |D_1|$ if $v_j \in D_2$). Also, the relational matrix is the square symmetric matrix such that the row or column corresponding to each $v_i \in D_1$ ($v_j \in D_2$) has the number of one's exactly equal to cardinality of D_2 (cardinality of D_1).

Remark 5.3. *If the entities follow complete Bipartite relation, then equation 4 reduces to the following form:*

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^2 \left[\frac{1}{|D_k|} \sum_{v_i \in D_k} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|D'_k|} \sum_{v_j \in D'_k} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{p+q}}$$

where D'_k denotes complement of the set D_k for every $k = 1, 2$.

5.1. Properties

Typically for a set arguments, the aggregated value obtained by f_G^{BM} depends on the underlying interrelationship among the arguments depicted via graph G . In the following propositions, we attempt to illustrate how the structural properties of G impacted the aggregated value by f_G^{BM} .

Proposition 5.1. *Let G and G' are the two isomorphic graphs and let $f : G \mapsto G'$ be the isomorphism between them. If the entities v_i and $f(v_i)$ carries same opinion values for every vertex $v_i \in G$, then the aggregated value obtained through f_G^{BM} corresponding to the graph G is equal to the aggregated value obtained through $f_{G'}^{BM}$ with correspondence to the graph G' .*

It is to be noted that converse of the remark 5.1 need not be true. Let $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ be the vertex set of the graph G with the corresponding opinion values $\{0.10, 0.20, 0.40\}$. Let G' be another graph with vertex set $V(G') = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ with the corresponding opinion values $\{0.10, 0.10, 0.20, 0.51\}$. Then both the graphs are not isomorphic, but we have $f_G^{BM} = f_{G'}^{BM}$.

Proposition 5.2. *If the graphs G_1 and G_2 be such that they both are connected with cardinality of each greater than equal to two, and $G_1 \cap G_2 = \emptyset$, then we have*

$$f_{G_1 \cup G_2}^{BM} \leq f_{G_1}^{BM} + f_{G_2}^{BM}$$

.

Proof. Applying equation 4 to the graph G_1 , we obtain the following equation:

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{|V(G_1)|} \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}}$$

Similarly, on applying equation 4 to the graph G_2 , the following equation is obtained:

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{|V(G_2)|} \sum_{v_i \in V(G_2)} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}}$$

On applying equation 4 to the graph $G_1 \cup G_2$, we obtained the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \left[\left\{ \frac{1}{|V(G_1)|} \sum_{v_i \in V(G_1)} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \right] \\ & + \left[\frac{1}{|V(G_2)|} \sum_{v_i \in V(G_2)} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{p+q}}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

From respective equations, it is evident that $f_{G_1 \cup G_2}^{BM} \leq f_{G_1}^{BM} + f_{G_2}^{BM}$. \square

Proposition 5.3. *If the graphs G_1 and G_2 be such that they are having components with cardinality of each component greater than equal to two, and $G_1 \cap G_2 = \emptyset$, then we have*

$$f_{G_1 \cup G_2}^{BM} \leq f_{G_1}^{BM} + f_{G_2}^{BM}$$

Example 5.1. *Let the graph G_1 has vertex set as $\{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ with opinion value as $\{0.2, 0.3, 0.1\}$ and let G_2 be subset of graph G_1 comprising of vertex $\{v_1, v_2\}$ with opinion value as $\{0.2, 0.3\}$. It can be seen as $f_{G_2}^{BM} > f_{G_1}^{BM}$. Thus, the aggregated value obtained through subset can be greater than the aggregated value attained through its superset.*

Proposition 5.4. *Let $f : G_1 \mapsto G_2$ be the isomorphism between two graphs G_1 and G_2 and let $g_1 : V(G_1) \mapsto [0, 1]$ be the function providing different opinion values to the entities in the graph G_1 . $g_2 : V(G_2) \mapsto [0, 1]$ be the function providing opinion values to entities of graph G_2 . If for every $i = 1, \dots, V(G_i)$, we have $g_1(v_i) \leq g_2(f(v_i))$, then*

$$f_{G_1}^{BM}(g_1(v_1), \dots, g_1(v_n)) \leq f_{G_2}^{BM}(g_2(f(v_1)), \dots, g_2(f(v_n))).$$

Proposition 5.5. *Let the graph G comprises of components P_1, \dots, P_d , where P_1, \dots, P_r are components with cardinality greater than equal to two, and the remaining components are of cardinality equal to one. Let $V(P_h) = \{v_1^h, \dots, v_{|P_h|}^h\}$ for every $h = 1, \dots, d$, where $V(P_h)$ denotes vertices in the component P_h . Let $\sigma_h : \{1, \dots, |P_h|\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, |P_h|\}$ be a permutation over indices of vertices in the component P_h ($h = 1, \dots, r$), which is chosen in such a manner that $E(P_h) = E(P_h^{\sigma_h})$, where $E(P_h^{\sigma_h})$ denotes the edge set obtained from the component P_h on replacing the vertices $v_i^h \in P_h$ by $\sigma_h(v_i^h) \forall i = 1, \dots, |P_h|$. Let $\sigma : \{r+1, \dots, d\} \mapsto \{r+1, \dots, d\}$ be permutation over indices of those components of graph G with cardinality equal to one. Then, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} f_G^{BM}(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) &= f_G^{BM}(g(v_1^1), \dots, g(v_{|P_1|}^1), \dots, g(v_1^r), \dots, g(v_{|P_r|}^r), g(v_1^{r+1}), \dots, g(v_1^d)) \\ &= f_G^{BM}(g(\sigma_1(v_1^1)), \dots, g(\sigma_1(v_{|P_1|}^1)), \dots, g(\sigma_r(v_1^r)), \dots, g(\sigma_r(v_{|P_r|}^r)), g(\sigma(v_1^{r+1})), \dots, g(\sigma(v_1^d))). \end{aligned}$$

Next, we proceed towards proposing the weighted form of the f_G^{BM} operator.

5.2. Weighted version of the f_G^{BM} operator

Consider a graph G comprising of components P_1, \dots, P_d , where P_1, \dots, P_r are components with cardinality greater than equal to two, and the remaining components are of cardinality equal to one. Let for every $v_i v_j \in E(P_h)$, $w_{ij}^h \geq 0$ denotes the weight of the corresponding edge in the component P_h adjoining vertices v_i and v_j . Since we are dealing with undirected graphs, so we have $w_{ij}^h = w_{ji}^h$. Note that here weights are provided to respective edges of different components. Then, the weighted form of the f_G^{BM} operator, denoted by Wf_G^{BM} , is defined as follows:

$$Wf_G^{BM}(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) = \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{h=1}^r \sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h}{|V(G)|} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{r} \sum_{h=1}^r \left(\frac{\sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ v_j \in N(v_i)}} w_{ij}^h (g(v_i))^p (g(v_j))^q}{\sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ v_j \in N(v_i)}} w_{ij}^h} \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \right\}^p + \left(\frac{\sum_{\substack{v_i \in V(G) \\ h \notin \{1, \dots, r\}}} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h}{|V(G)|} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{\substack{v_i \in V(G) \\ h \notin \{1, \dots, r\}}} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ |P_h|=1}} (g(v_i))^p \right\}^{\frac{1}{p}} \right] \quad (12)$$

Here $w_{ij}^h \geq 0$ represents positive interaction of edges joining vertices v_i, v_j in the component P_h .

The form given in equation 12 can be well utilized in the complex medical systems where the patient need to be prescribed treatment based on his/ her respective symptoms. The symptoms may be considered as different vertices and an edge exists between pair of symptoms if those two symptoms are apparent in a patient's body for possibly expected diseases. Weights given to the respective edges enables to describe the degree or intensity of a particular pair of symptoms effectual in detection of a particular disease.

We propose another form of weighted f_G^{BM} operator that considers not only weights of interactions among entities, but also takes into consideration weights of individuals as well.

Let for every $v_i v_j \in E(P_h)$, $w_{ij}^h \geq 0$ denotes the weight of the edge in the component P_h adjoining vertices v_i and v_j . Let (w_1, \dots, w_n) be the weights assigned to individual entities, where each $w_i \geq 0$ represents weight of the entity $v_i \in V(G)$. Then the compounded weighted form of f_G^{BM} operator, denoted by $CWf_G^{BM} : [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$, and is defined as follows:

$$CWf_G^{BM}(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) = \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^r w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{r} \sum_{h=1}^r \left(\frac{\sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ v_j \in N(v_i)}} w_{ij}^h (g(v_i))^p (g(v_j))^q}{\sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ v_j \in N(v_i)}} w_{ij}^h} \right)^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \right\}^p + \left(\frac{\sum_{i \notin \{1, \dots, r\}} w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{i \notin \{1, \dots, r\}} w_i} \sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ |P_h|=1}} w_i (g(v_i))^p \right\}^{\frac{1}{p}} \right] \quad (13)$$

Equation 13 enables us to take into consideration interactional weights among entities along with the individual weights which makes the framework more flexible for decision systems.

Remark 5.4. In most of the weighted versions of the BM operator available in the following literature [26–28, 41–

43], first a specified structure of interrelationship pattern among the inputs is assumed beforehand, then the weights are given to the inputs based on that pre-defined relationship pattern. But in the proposed weighted forms given by the Wf_G^{BM} and the CWf_G^{BM} operator, the generalized pattern of interrelationship structure among the inputs depicted through a graph is considered and then the interaction weights are assigned to the respective pair of inputs only if the concerned pair are interlinked together via an edge. The differences between few weighted forms of the BM operator and the proposed weighted forms are mentioned in Table I.

In column 3 of Table I, it has been described whether the relationship among inputs/entities are assumed or not. In column 4, the relationship type among inputs is described. Column 5 describes whether the mentioned form of BM operator has a coalition of dependent or independent inputs. In column 6, the description of weights are given. In column 7, the description of the idempotent behavior of operators has been given. Last column describes whether the operator behavior changes on change in relationship pattern or not. For instance, in the WIBM operator [43], the relationship among inputs is assumed beforehand. It is an idempotent operator and takes direct homogeneous interaction among dependent inputs. Also, it considers only interactive weights of inputs and its behavior does not change on change in a relationship pattern. Similarly, information regarding other weighted versions of the BM operator mentioned in the table can be interpreted.

In the proposed Wf_G^{BM} operator, the relationship structure among inputs is not assumed beforehand and is shown via graph. The inputs comprise dependent and independent entities and interactive weights are assigned based on the relationships depicted through the edges of the graph. The proposed operator is idempotent and the output value changes abruptly on a slight change in the relationship pattern. The proposed Wf_G^{BM} operator has been further improved by proposing CWf_G^{BM} operator that takes both interactive and individual weights into consideration.

It is important to note here that there are also proposals regarding weighted forms of BM operator in which the weights are learned via data-driven approach. Specifically, the weights of BM were learnt from human judgments of species diversity via linear fitting method in [44], while a more comprehensive framework to learn weights for generalized BM from dataset containing inputs and outputs of a aggregation system were proposed in [45]. The proposed versions of weighted BM operator only considers the interrelationship semantics which is described through graph, and based on that graph-based interconnections, weight allocation mechanism has been proposed.

Table I: Different weighted extensions of the BM operator and their relative differences

Forms	Reference	Relation	Relation-type	Input-type	Weights type	Idempotency	Behavior
GWBM	[41]	Assumed	Homogeneous	Dependent	Individual	Non-idempotent	No change
NWBM	[42]	Assumed	Homogeneous	Dependent	Individual	idempotent	No change
WIBM	[43]	Assumed	Homogeneous	Dependent	Interactive	idempotent	No change
CWIBM	[43]	Assumed	Homogeneous	Dependent	Interactive and individual	idempotent	No change
WPBM	[26]	Assumed	Partition-wise Homogeneous	Dependent	Individual	Idempotent	Partition-based
WEBM	[27]	Assumed	Heterogeneous	Dependent and independent	Individual	Idempotent	Changes
WEPBM	[28]	Assumed	Partition-wise Heterogeneous	Dependent	Individual	Idempotent	Partition-based
Wf_G^{BM}		Not assumed	Generalized	Dependent and independent	interactive	Idempotent	Changes
CWf_G^{BM}		Not assumed	Generalized	Dependent and independent	interactive and individual	Idempotent	Changes

Next, we proceed towards proposing generalized version of the f_G^{BM} operator.

6. Generalized f_G^{BM} operator to apprehend mandatory prerequisites

This section progresses towards proposing a subtle framework of an information fusion system by manifesting a more generalized variant of the f_G^{BM} operator in such a precise way that it engrosses the mandatory conditions that exist within the decision system in an exceptional environment where the alliance among different entities is portrayed through different graphical patterns.

We initiate the framework of the generalized system by considering a special case of interconnections among different entities. We consider a graph G comprising of d number of components P_1, \dots, P_d where P_1, \dots, P_r are components with cardinality greater than equal to two and the remaining are the components with cardinality equal to one. We assume that P_m be the component with the condition that $|P_m| \geq 2$ and it is the only component in the graph G which is complete, i.e. all the entities in P_m are directly dependent on each other. In such a precise case, the satisfaction level obtained from the component P_m can be evaluated through the following function:

$$\left[\frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^m} \sum_{v_i \in P_m} (g(v_i))^{l_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{(\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^m - 1) \dots (\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^m - k + 1)} \sum_{v_{i_2} \neq \dots \neq v_{i_k} \in N(v_i)} (g(v_{i_2}))^{l_2} \dots (g(v_{i_k}))^{l_k} \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{l_1 + \dots + l_k}} \quad (14)$$

where

$$\mathbb{1}_{v_i}^m = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } v_i \in P_m \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and $2 \leq k \leq |P_m|$, $l_1, \dots, l_k \geq 0$ with the condition that $l_1 + \dots + l_k > 0$.

Thus, the revised or the modulated version of the f_G^{BM} operator can be expressed by the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{h=1}^r \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h}{|V(G)|} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{r} \left\{ \sum_{\substack{h=1 \\ h \neq m}}^r \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ h \neq m}} (g(v_i))^{l_1} \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^{l_2} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{l_1+l_2}} + \left\{ \right. \right. \right. \quad (15) \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^m} \sum_{v_i \in P_m} (g(v_i))^{l_1} \left(\frac{1}{(\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^m - 1) \dots (\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^m - k + 1)} \right. \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \sum_{v_{i_2} \neq \dots \neq v_{i_k} \in N(v_i)} (g(v_{i_2}))^{l_2} \dots (g(v_{i_k}))^{l_k} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{l_1+l_2+\dots+l_k}} \right\}^{l_1} + \left(\frac{\sum_{h \notin \{1, \dots, r\}} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h}{|V(G)|} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sum_{\substack{v_i \in V(G) \\ h \notin \{1, \dots, r\}}} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{\substack{v_i \in P_h \\ |P_h|=1}} (g(v_i))^{l_1} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{l_1}}
\end{aligned}$$

with the convention that $\frac{0}{0} = 1$. The operator given in equation 14 evaluates the satisfaction level attained from the complete component P_m of the graph G by taking conjunctions of opinion values of k directly related entities. This enables us to impose the mandatory constraint that in order to get a non-zero satisfaction level from the complete component P_m , at least the opinion value of k number of directly related entities should be positive. The parameter value k administers the flexibility of the proposed operator. It can be further noted that the condition that P_m is complete is not necessary for the equations 14, 15. One may take P_m as a p -regular graph where degree of each vertex in P_m is p , and $p \geq 1$; then one may take $2 \leq k \leq p + 1$. The concept of the imposed mandatory conditions can be further explained through the following example.

Example 6.1. Consider a simple connected graph G which is also complete. Let $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$ be the vertex set. We consider the MCDM problem where $V(G)$ represents the set of criteria following which the performance level of different candidates has to be evaluated. Suppose a candidate has to be selected based on his/ her performance over respective criteria with the condition that the performance of the candidate in at least three directly related entities/ criteria should be positive. If opinion values or criteria values $g(v_i)$ obtained by a candidate over the criteria set $V(G)$ are as follows: $\{g(v_1), g(v_2), g(v_3), g(v_4)\} = \{0.2, 0, 0.3, 0\}$, then by applying the f_G^{BM} operator, the aggregated value obtained is positive. But, it is to be noted that the candidate is not able to satisfy the given mandatory condition of getting at least three positive opinion values of directly related entities/ criteria. This shows that the f_G^{BM} operator proposed in section 5 is not able to uphold the mandatory requisites, while if we take $k = 3$ in equation 14, we get the performance value of the candidate as zero, which shows that the operator given by equations 14 and 15 are able to uphold the mandatory prerequisites of the decision system.

Remark 6.1. The operator given by 15 can be further extended to the case where more than one number of components are complete or regular. For framing such an operator, we assume that out of P_1, \dots, P_r components with the cardinality of each greater than equal to two, P_1, \dots, P_t are the components which are complete, and the rest are not complete components. If we denote the performance value obtained by the component P_h by p_h , then

for each $h = 1, \dots, t$ the value p_h can be determined by the following equation:

$$\left[\frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{v_i \in P_h} (g(v_i))^{l_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{(\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h - 1) \dots (\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h - k_h + 1)} \sum_{v_{i_2} \neq \dots \neq v_{i_{k_h}} \in N(v_i)} (g(v_{i_2}))^{l_2} \dots (g(v_{i_{k_h}}))^{l_{k_h}} \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{l_1 + \dots + l_{k_h}}} \quad (16)$$

$\forall h = 1, \dots, t$ and the parameter value k_h satisfies $2 \leq k_h \leq |P_h|$.

It is to be noted that here k_h depends on the considered component P_h , thus enabling to impose different mandatory conditions on different complete components with cardinality of each greater than equal to two. If one wishes to impose same mandatory conditions for each complete component P_h where $h = 1, \dots, t$, then one may take $k_h = k$ where $2 \leq k \leq \min_{h=1}^t |P_h|$.

From the above discussion it is comprehensible that for the formulation of any fusion function for gathering accumulated information, there are two aspects that are to be taken into consideration. First, the function must consider the interconnections among different entities, and second, the function should be able to uphold the mandatory conditions of the decision system. Thus there is an enormous need to generalize the f_G^{BM} operator that can perfectly handle the mandatory requisites.

6.1. Generalized variation of the f_G^{BM} operator

We initiate proposing the generalized model of the f_G^{BM} operator by investigating on how operators are functioning within the components P_h of the graph G . Let p_h is the accumulated opinion value attained from the component P_h of G with $|P_h| \geq 2$, then in the f_G^{BM} operator, p_h is given by the equation:

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^h} \sum_{v_i \in P_h} (g(v_i))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} (g(v_j))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}}.$$

The principle idea of constructing this form of p_h in the f_G^{BM} operator is described as follows. Consider a particular component P_h with $|P_h| \geq 2$.

1. For each $v_i \in P_h$, consider the neighborhood $N(v_i)$. In the proposed f_G^{BM} operator, the opinion value of all the entities in $N(v_i)$ are aggregated through the q^{th} power arithmetic mean operator. One may choose a generalized function say M_2^h to aggregate the opinion values of the entities in $N(v_i)$ based on the mandatory requirements to be satisfied by the decision systems. Then we have $M_2^h : \cup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$ (where \mathbb{N} is the set of all natural numbers). Thus, the expression

$$M_2^h(g(v_j) : v_j \in N(v_i))$$

provides accumulated opinion value from the entities in $N(v_i)$. Different choice of M_2^h imposes different

mandatory conditions.

2. In the proposed f_G^{BM} operator, the opinion value attained from the considered entity $v_i \in P_h$ AND the accumulated opinion value attained from all the entities in $N(v_i)$ (given by the expression $M_2^h(g(v_j) : v_j \in N(v_i))$) are adjoined together by using a conjunctive operator $C(x, y) = x^p y^q$, where $C : [0, 1]^2 \mapsto [0, 1]$. One may choose different conjunctive operator say C^h to evaluate the conjunction between opinion value of the respective entity v_i and the accumulated opinion value attained from the entities in $N(v_i)$. Thus, the expression

$$C^h\left(g(v_i), M_2^h(g(v_j) : v_j \in N(v_i))\right)$$

evaluates the conjunction of the opinion value attained from the entity v_i AND the entities in $N(v_i)$.

3. The above mentioned steps are repeated for every $v_i \in P_h$ and the final accumulated opinion value attained from the component P_h is obtained by employing the arithmetic mean operator in the proposed f_G^{BM} . For generalization aspect, one may replace the arithmetic mean operator by other operator say $M_1^h : [0, 1]^{|P_h|} \mapsto [0, 1]$, and is in accordance with the mandatory conditions to be imposed by the decision systems. Thus, the expression

$$M_1^h\left\{C^h\left(g(v_i), M_2^h\{g(v_j) : v_j \in N(v_i)\}\right) : v_i \in P_h\right\}$$

evaluates the accumulated opinion value attained from the component P_h . In order to preserve the idempotency property, one may apply the function $\delta_{C^h}^{-1}$ over the resultant form. Thus, the expression

$$p_h = \delta_{C^h}^{-1}\left[M_1^h\left\{C^h\left(g(v_i), M_2^h\{g(v_j) : v_j \in N(v_i)\}\right) : v_i \in P_h\right\}\right] \quad (17)$$

provides the accumulated opinion value from the component P_h , where $|P_h| \geq 2$.

The procedure of obtaining the accumulated opinion value p_h from the component P_h as discussed above can be carried out for all the components of G with cardinality greater than equal to two. Then the accumulated opinion value obtained from all the components P_h where $h = 1, \dots, r$ can be obtained by employing the function $\bar{M}_1 : [0, 1]^r \mapsto [0, 1]$. In the corresponding f_G^{BM} operator, \bar{M}_1 was taken as the arithmetic mean operator. Thus the generalized form of the function which enables us to evaluate the accumulated opinion value attained through all the components P_h where $h = 1, \dots, r$ can be attained through the following expression:

$$\bar{M}_1\left[\delta_{C^h}^{-1}\left\{M_1^h\left\{C^h\left(g(v_i), M_2^h\{g(v_j) : v_j \in N(v_i)\}\right) : v_i \in P_h\right\}\right\} : h = 1, \dots, r\right] \quad (18)$$

Example 6.2. Consider a graph with two components P_1 and P_2 where $V(P_1) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4\}$, $V(P_2) = \{v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8\}$, such that component P_1 is complete and $E(P_2) = \{v_5v_6, v_6v_7, v_7v_5, v_5v_8\}$. It has been decided by the decision system that in order to evaluate the accumulated opinion value from the component P_1 , the opinion values of at least three directly related entities should be positive; and for evaluating the accumulated opinion value from the set P_2 , the opinion values of at least two directly related entities should be positive. Also, it is required

to get accumulated positive opinions from both the components.

For computing the accumulated opinion values from the components P_1 and P_2 as per mentioned mandatory requisites, one may take the following generalized form of the functions p_1 and p_2 ,

$$p_1 = \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^1} \sum_{v_i \in P_1} g(v_i) \left(\frac{1}{(\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^1 - 1)(\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^1 - 2)} \sum_{\substack{v_j, v_k \in N(v_i) \\ j \neq k}} g(v_j)g(v_k) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$p_2 = \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{v_i \in V(G)} \mathbb{1}_{v_i}^2} \sum_{v_i \in P_2} g(v_i) \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i)|} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} g(v_j) \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Here, we have taken $M_1^1 = M_2^2 = M_1^2 =$ arithmetic mean operator, $M_2^1 =$ Bonferroni mean (BM), $C^1(x, y) = C^2(x, y) = x.y$. Now, in order to satisfy the requirement that accumulated opinion values in both the components P_1 and P_2 given by p_1, p_2 , respectively, should be positive, we take the generalized form of the f_G^{BM} operator as $(p_1 p_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

It is to be noted that equation 18 provides the generalized expression of evaluating the accumulated opinion value attained from all the components of graph G with cardinality of each greater than equal to two. Next, it is desirable to obtain a generalized expression for evaluating the accumulated opinion value attained from all the components of G with cardinality equals one that also combats with the mandatory requirements. One may utilize the function say \bar{M}_2 , where $\bar{M}_2 : [0, 1]^{d-r} \mapsto [0, 1]$ to evaluate the accumulated opinion value of components with cardinality equals one. The function \bar{M}_2 may vary depending on the mandatory prerequisites of decision systems. In the graph G , the components P_{r+1}, \dots, P_d are of cardinality one (total $(d-r)$ number of components with cardinality equal to one), let p_{r+i} symbolizes the opinion value attained from the component P_{r+i} where $i = 1, \dots, d-r$. Then,

$$\bar{M}_2(p_{r+1}, \dots, p_d) \tag{19}$$

represents the accumulated opinion value attained from all the components of G with cardinality equals one.

Now to procure the opinion value attained through amalgamation of components with cardinality greater than equal to two and the components with cardinality equals one of the graph G , one wishes to utilize a function $M : [0, 1]^2 \mapsto [0, 1]$, and then the final aggregated opinion value is obtainable through the following operator given in the next definition.

Definition 17. Let G be the generalized graph with components P_1, \dots, P_d , where P_1, \dots, P_r are components with cardinality greater than equal to two, and the rest of the components are of cardinality one. The generalized variation of the f_G^{BM} operator, denoted by f_G^* , is the function $f_G^* : [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$, and is given by the following

form:

$$f_G^*(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) = M \left[\bar{M}_1 \left\{ \delta_{C^h}^{-1} \left\{ M_1^h \left\{ C^h \left(g(v_i), M_2^h \{ g(v_j) : v_j \in N(v_i) \} \right) : v_i \in P_h \right\} : h = 1, \dots, r \right\} \right\} \right. \\ \left. \bar{M}_2(p_{r+1}, \dots, p_d) \right] \quad (20)$$

where $M : [0, 1]^2 \mapsto [0, 1]$, $\bar{M}_1 : [0, 1]^r \mapsto [0, 1]$, $\bar{M}_2 : [0, 1]^{d-r} \mapsto [0, 1]$, $M_1^h : [0, 1]^{|P_h|} \mapsto [0, 1]$, $M_2^h : \cup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [0, 1]^n \mapsto [0, 1]$, $C^h : [0, 1]^2 \mapsto [0, 1]$, $\delta_{C^h}^{-1} : [0, 1] \mapsto [0, 1]$ denotes the inverse diagonal of the function C^h where the diagonal of C^h (δ_{C^h}) is given by $\delta_{C^h}(t) = C^h(t, t)$, and p_{r+i} is the opinion value of the component P_{r+i} for every $i = 1, \dots, d - r$.

Example 6.3. Consider a graph G comprising of four components P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4 , where P_1 and P_2 are complete subgraphs with cardinality 3 and 4 respectively, and P_3 and P_4 each are of cardinality one. We consider the MCDM problem with the vertex set $V(G)$ as the criteria set. Suppose a candidate has to be selected based on his/her performance over the criteria set $V(G)$. In order to select the foremost candidate, the following mandatory conditions are imposed by the decision system: It is necessary to get positive accumulated opinion value or satisfaction level from all the components; for computing the accumulated satisfaction level for the component P_1 , performance values or opinion values of at least two directly related criteria/entities should be positive; for computing the accumulated satisfaction level for the component P_2 , performance values or opinion values of at least three directly related entities should be positive.

Then, one may take M_1^1, M_2^1, M_1^2 as the arithmetic mean operator, M_2^2 as the Bonferroni mean (BM) operator with $p = 1 = q$ $C^1(x, y) = x.y = C^2(x, y)$, \bar{M}_1, \bar{M}_2, M may be taken as the geometric mean operator. The resultant operator f_G^* is obtained as follows:

$$f_G^*(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) = \left[\left\{ \left\{ \frac{1}{3} \sum_{v_i \in P_1} g(v_i) \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} g(v_j) \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left\{ \frac{1}{4} \sum_{v_i \in P_2} g(v_i) \left(\frac{1}{6} \sum_{v_j \neq v_k \in N(v_i)} g(v_j)g(v_k) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right. \\ \left. \left(\prod_{v_i \in P_3, P_4} g(v_i) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

If we reform the mandatory conditions by: It is required to get positive performance level in at least one of P_1 and P_2 , but it is mandatory to perform well in the components P_3 and P_4 ; in order to get desired satisfaction level from P_1 , the opinion values of at least three directly related entities should be positive; for computing the satisfaction level for component P_2 , opinion value of at least two directly related entities should be positive.

Then, one may take $M_1^1, M_2^1, M_1^2, \bar{M}_1$ as the arithmetic mean, $M_2^2 =$ Bonferroni mean (BM) operator with $p = 1 = q$, $C^1(x, y) = C^2(x, y) = x.y$, \bar{M}_2, M as the geometric mean operator. Then the operator f_G^* takes the

following form:

$$f_G^*(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) = \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \right) \left\{ \left\{ \frac{1}{3} \sum_{v_i \in P_1} g(v_i) \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{v_j \neq v_k \in N(v_i)} g(v_j)g(v_k) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left\{ \frac{1}{4} \sum_{v_i \in P_2} g(v_i) \left(\frac{1}{3} \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} g(v_j) \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} \left(\prod_{v_i \in P_3, P_4} g(v_i) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Remark 6.2. Let G_1 and G_2 are the two isomorphic graphs and let $T : G_1 \mapsto G_2$ be an onto isomorphism between them. Let $g(v_i) = g(T(v_i))$ for every $v_i \in V(G_1)$. Then, we have $f_{G_1}^*(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) = f_{G_2}^*(g(T(v_1)), \dots, g(T(v_n)))$.

Remark 6.3. Let the graph G comprises of components P_1, \dots, P_d , where P_1, \dots, P_r are components with cardinality greater than equal to two, and the remaining components are of cardinality equal to one. Let $V(P_h) = \{v_1^h, \dots, v_{|P_h|}^h\}$ denote the vertex set of P_h for every $h = 1, \dots, d$. Let $\sigma_h : \{1, \dots, |P_h|\} \mapsto \{1, \dots, |P_h|\}$ be a permutation over indices of vertices in the component P_h for each $h = 1, \dots, r$, which is chosen in such a manner that $E(P_h) = E(P_h^{\sigma_h})$, where $E(P_h^{\sigma_h})$ denotes the edge set obtained by the component P_h on replacing the vertices $v_j^h \in P_h$ by $\sigma_h(v_j^h) \forall j = 1, \dots, |P_h|$. This is done for every $h = 1, \dots, r$. Let $\sigma : \{r+1, \dots, d\} \mapsto \{r+1, \dots, d\}$ be permutation over indices of those components with cardinality equal to one. Then, if $M_1^h, M_2^h, \bar{M}_1, \bar{M}_2$, and M are commutative operators for every $h = 1, \dots, r$ (irrespective of the operator C^h), we have

$$\begin{aligned} f_G^*(g(v_1), \dots, g(v_n)) &= f_G^*(g(v_1^1), \dots, g(v_{|P_1|}^1), \dots, g(v_1^r), \dots, g(v_{|P_r|}^r), g(v_1^{r+1}), \dots, g(v_1^d)) \\ &= f_G^*(g(\sigma_1(v_1^1)), \dots, g(\sigma_1(v_{|P_1|}^1)), \dots, g(\sigma_r(v_1^r)), \dots, g(\sigma_r(v_{|P_r|}^r)), g(\sigma(v_1^{r+1})), \dots, g(\sigma(v_1^d))) \end{aligned}$$

Remark 6.4. The summary of advantages of the proposed f_G^{BM} operator and its generalization f_G^* over some other available extensions and generalizations of the BM operator is given in Table II. The fourth column describes whether the relationship among inputs or entities is assumed or not, and the fifth column describes the type of relationship pattern handled by the particular form of the BM operator. The sixth column describes whether the inputs considered are dependent or independent in nature. In the seventh column, the capability of the operator to handle mandatory conditions is discussed and in the eighth column, the behavior of the operator on a change in the relationship pattern among the inputs is inspected. The last column describes the mentioned form of BM operator is attainable from which other forms of the BM.

The form of BM operator given by Yager in [25] assumes a homogeneous relationship structure among all the dependent inputs. Such a form of BM operator handles a specific form of the mandatory condition and can be easily obtainable from other mentioned forms of BM in the table. Also, the behavior of this operator does not changes while changing the relationship pattern among inputs. In a similar way, the information about other mentioned forms of BM can be interpreted.

The proposed f_G^{BM} operator handles any generalized structure of the relationship pattern among the dependent

and independent inputs and responds abruptly to a slight modification in the relationship pattern. Such a proposed operator can handle a specific form of the mandatory condition. In order to regulate the issue of handling any type of mandatory conditions by the system, the improved form of the f_G^{BM} operator, namely f_G^* has been proposed by generalizing the f_G^{BM} operator. The mentioned forms of the BM operator in Table II can be attainable from the proposed operator f_G^* , justifying its flexibility in handling real-world problems.

Table II: Different forms of BM operator vs the current study along with their relative differences

#	Forms	Reference	Relation	Relation-type	Input-type	Mandatory condition	Behavior	Attainability
1	BM(Yager)	[25]	Assumed	Homogeneous	Dependent	Specific	No change	2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9
2	PBM	[26]	Assumed	Partition-wise Homogeneous	Dependent	Specific	Partition based	4,6,8,9
3	EBM	[27]	Assumed	Heterogeneous	Dependent and independent	Specific	Changes	7,8,9
4	EPBM	[28]	Assumed	Partition-wise Heterogeneous	Dependent	Specific	Partition based	8,9
5	GBM	[7]	Assumed	Homogeneous	Dependent	Generalized	No change	6,7,8,9
6	GPBM	[30]	Assumed	Partition-wise Homogeneous	Dependent	Generalized	Partition based	8,9
7	GEBM	[46]	Assumed	Heterogeneous	Dependent and independent	Generalized	Changes	8,9
8	f_G^{BM}		Not assumed	Generalized	Dependent and independent	Specific	Changes	9
9	f_G^*		Not assumed	Generalized	Dependent and independent	Generalized	Changes	

Next, we proceed towards an applicatory part where we utilize the proposed operator over the Hacker attack system.

7. Application of the proposed operators over the Hacker Attack System

Suppose a hacker wishes to attack the network system of an organization. His/ her primary goal is to damage the considered network system as worst as possible. There may be several plans available to the hacker which are formulated by experts based on the current global situation. The hacker needs to inspect each of the available plans and then select the best plan which maximizes disruption in the smooth functioning of the network system. Undoubtedly, if a particular plan has been put into action, then there will be some degree of effect over different units of the network system. These effect degree over different units will be utilized to assess the available plans.

We assume that an organization's network system comprises several branches/ agents located in different states. One can effortlessly characterize the considered situation through a graph G , where the vertices or nodes are the different branches/ agents of the network system, and the sub-network of agents in different states may be represented by different components of G . Let $V(G)$ be the set of agents which the hacker wishes to strike on. Specifically, we assume that there are d states that are described by the graph components $\{P_1, \dots, P_d\}$ of G . Here, we assume that $|P_h| \geq 2 \forall h = 1, \dots, d$. The association or coordination among the branches or agents can be portrayed through the edges of the graph. Let the set $E(G)$ describe the association among the agents. Suppose that there are $Y = \{Y_1, \dots, Y_m\}$ plans available to the hacker, then the aim of the hacker is

to identify that particular plan from Y that could make maximum disruption in the smooth functioning of the organization's network system. In order to do so, one requires to formulate a proper model that enables us to quantify the disruption intensity caused by a particular attack plan in terms of the benefits of the hacker. In the subsequent work, we provide a descriptive model that is able to evaluate the overall benefit degrees retrieved from each of the available plans by utilizing the proposal of generalized f_G^{BM} operator whose formulation is based on the mandatory requisites of the decision system. Also, it can be employed in a suitable environment where connections among agents are portrayed through a graphical structure.

1. Assigning weights to the agents based on the network structure

At first, for each state P_h , weights must be assigned to all the agents in P_h . These weights depict the importance of each agent in the considered sub-network of the state P_h . For assigning the weights, we adopt the following ideology. That particular agent of the state P_h is of higher importance if removing it leads to an increase in the number of disconnected components of P_h . This idea of assigning weights to the agents is quite appropriate in the vision of the Hacker attack system, as that agent will be highly important to the hacker if on striking it leads to disconnection and non-coordination among other available agents of the considered sub-network P_h . An increase in the number of components of the state P_h leads to miscommunication and failure of assistance or support from other agents to the targeted agent which further leads to the failure of the system of the considered sub-network. Thus, if removing a particular agent of the state results in an increase in the number of components of the considered state, then that branch/ agent is of higher importance.

Let the number of components attained on removing the agents of a state P_h are n_1, n_2, \dots, n_l where $n_1 > \dots > n_l$.

If $l = 1$, which happens when same number of components are attained on removing any agent of the state P_h , then for agent $v_i^h \in P_h$, assign the weight $w_i^h = \frac{1}{|P_h|} \forall v_i^h \in P_h$, where $|P_h|$ denotes number of agents in the considered state P_h .

If $l > 1$, then define $P_h^j \subset P_h$, given by

$$P_h^j = \{v_i^h : v_i^h \in P_h, \text{ number of components left on removing } v_i^h \text{ is } n_j\}.$$

Then, the weights are assigned as follows. If $v_i^h \in P_h^j$, for every $j = \{1, \dots, l-1\}$ then

$$w_i^h = \frac{1}{2^j |P_h^j|} \quad (21)$$

and, for each $v_i^h \in P_h^l$ we have,

$$w_i^h = \frac{1 - (\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^{l-1}})}{|P_h^l|}. \quad (22)$$

Similarly, one can calculate the weights of agents of the other respective states.

2. **A protocol must be contemplated by which the benefit degree obtained from the plan Y by attacking a particular agent of the considered state can be evaluated by the hacker.**

The hacker may have several available plans. Some plans may affect a particular agent, while some may not. We wish to evaluate the degree of effect or the degree of benefit retrieved by the hacker on implementing a particular plan Y while targeting a particular agent, say $v_i^h \in P_h$.

Suppose a hacker implements a plan Y . On considering the agent $v_i^h \in P_h$, if the agent is directly affected by the plan Y , then we denote $t_i^h = 1$, otherwise we take $t_i^h = 0$. Let $g_Y(v_i^h)$ denote the degree of benefit reaped by the hacker from agent $v_i^h \in P_h$ on implementing plan Y , and is given by

$$g_Y(v_i^h) = \frac{t_i^h + \sum_{j \in N(v_i^h)} \xi_{ij} t_j^h}{|P_h|} \quad \forall v_i^h \in P_h \quad (23)$$

where $N(v_i^h)$ is the neighboring agents of v_i^h , $\xi_{ij} = w_i^h w_j^h$ is the degree of association between the agent v_i^h and the neighboring agent $v_j^h \in N(v_i^h)$.

3. **By utilizing the benefit degrees reaped by the hacker on attacking the agents of the state P_h , evaluate the accumulated benefit degree obtained by the considered state P_h .**

On considering a particular state P_h , the benefit degree reaped by the agents $v_i^h \in P_h$ is given by $g_Y(v_i^h)$. The accumulated benefit degree reaped by the state P_h , denoted by p_h^Y , is evaluated by utilizing equation (7), and is given by the following form:

$$p_h^Y = \left\{ \frac{1}{|P_h|} \sum_{v_i^h \in P_h} (g_Y(v_i^h))^p \left(\frac{1}{|N(v_i^h)|} \sum_{v_j^h \in N(v_i^h)} (g_Y(v_j^h))^q \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{p+q}} \quad (24)$$

Then, the accumulated benefit degree obtained from the state P_h , given by p_h^Y , is evaluated for each state P_h where $h = 1, \dots, d$ and for each plan $Y \in \{Y_1, \dots, Y_m\}$.

4. **Some prioritization is needed to be assigned to the respective states.**

In the contemporary situation, there always exists a prioritization among the respective states. From the hacker's perspective, prioritization may be given to states based on the number of agents in each state. There may be other perspectives for assigning priorities, for instance, those states which are highly developed are more prioritized as compared to the under-developed states. States may also be prioritized based on the significance of each state in maintaining proper coordination and managerial activities of the organization's network system. For example, on the battlefield, army men working in the management unit are more prioritized as compared to the army men in the other units. If we assign prioritization based on the number of agents in each state, then without loss of generality, one may assume that the available states P_h are such that $|P_1| > \dots > |P_d| \geq 2$, where $|P_h|$ denotes the number of agents in the state P_h .

5. **Assigning weights to the states based on the prioritization given to them.**

Based on the prioritization assigned to the states, one wishes to obtain respective weights for them. We

utilize the idea given in [47], where weights assigned to the states are dependent on the benefit degree attained from the higher prioritized states. For each state P_h , we have the accumulated benefit degree as p_h^Y . The weight for the state P_h , denoted by w_h^Y , is assigned as follows. Set $w_1^Y = 1$ and

$$w_h^Y = 1 \cdot p_1^Y \cdot p_2^Y \dots p_{h-1}^Y \quad \forall h = 2, \dots, d. \quad (25)$$

The weights to the states are assigned in a way that a lower benefit degree obtained from a higher prioritized state cannot be compensated by a higher benefit degree from a lower prioritized state.

6. By assuming desired mandatory conditions, the final aggregated benefit degree obtained from all the respective states by implementing plan Y , denoted by f_G^{*Y} can be evaluated.

Next, by utilizing the benefit degree attained from the respective states P_h , symbolized by p_h^Y , and the assigned weights w_h^Y for each $h = 1, \dots, d$, we evaluate the final aggregated benefit degree obtained by the plan Y , denoted by f_G^{*Y} as follows:

$$f_G^{*Y} = \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i_1 \neq \dots \neq i_k = 1}^d w_{i_1}^Y (p_{i_1}^Y)^{l_1} \dots w_{i_k}^Y (p_{i_k}^Y)^{l_k}}{\sum_{i_1 \neq \dots \neq i_k = 1}^d w_{i_1}^Y \dots w_{i_k}^Y} \right\}^{\frac{1}{l_1 + \dots + l_k}} \quad (26)$$

where the parameter k is responsible for controlling the mandatory requirements of the decision system.

The mandatory requirements of the decision system can be imposed by taking different value of k . One can take the parameter value $k = 1, \dots, d$. By choosing different k , one can rank the best and the worst plan among the available plans on changing the mandatory requisites. For instance, if we take $k = d - 1$, then non-zero aggregated benefit value f_G^{*Y} from plan Y will be obtained only if at the most one value from the set $\{p_h^Y : h = 1, \dots, d\}$ is zero. This means that taking parameter value as $k = d - 1$ ensures that the benefit degree obtained from all the respective states should be non-zero with exception of at the most one state.

With the proposed model, the hacker could quantify the possible benefit reaped from any attack plan, provided the network structure of agents is portrayed in the form of a graph. Based on this principle, we design an algorithm 1, to obtain the best possible attack plan from the available plans in terms of the hacker's benefit.

Algorithm 1: Hacker Attack System

- 1 **Input:** Set of plans $\{Y_1, \dots, Y_m\}$ and a graph G with components P_1, \dots, P_d such that $|P_1| > |P_2| > \dots > |P_d| \geq 2$, where $|P_h|$ denotes the number of agents in the respective state P_h .
- 2 **Output:** Ranking of available plans based on the graph G .
- 3 STEP 1) For each state P_h , calculate the weights w_i^h corresponding to each agent $v_i^h \in P_h$ by utilizing equations (21), (22).
- 4 **for** each plan $Y \in \{Y_1, \dots, Y_m\}$, **do**
- 5 STEP 2: Evaluate the benefit degree reaped by each agent $v_i^h \in P_h$, denoted by $g_Y(v_i^h)$ by utilizing equation (23) $\forall h = 1, \dots, d$.
- 6 STEP 3: Calculate the accumulated benefit degree attained by the respective state P_h , denoted by p_h^Y by utilizing equation (24), for every $h = 1, \dots, d$.
- 7 STEP 3: Assign weights w_h^Y to the available states P_h based on the given prioritization relationship among them as stated in equation (25).
- 8 STEP 4: Compute the final aggregated benefit degree f_G^{*Y} obtained from the plan Y by utilizing equation (26).
- 9 **end**
- 10 STEP 5) Rank the plans based on the calculated values f_G^{*Y} .

Given the graph G that effectively describes the network structure of agents and the available attack plans in hands of the hacker, the Algorithm 1 can provide rank to the attack plans based on the overall benefit degree retrieved by striking respective agents of different states. One can easily implement this algorithm in any programming language with a supporting library for data structures such as graphs, standard graph algorithms, networks, etc. However, we have implemented the algorithm in Python for our numerical computations and used `NetworkX`¹ library to handle graphs and network.

Next, we provide a didactic example to illustrate the working of the proposed algorithm. Specifically, we intend to mimic the practical scenario of an organization, whose network of agents has extended over four states, and the hacker's aim is to disrupt the smooth functioning of the organization's network system with a particular plan Y that maximizes the intensity of disruption. The network of the organization is represented by the graph G comprising of four connected components P_1 , P_2 , P_3 , and P_4 . The agents are described in the set $V(G) = \{v_1, \dots, v_{32}\}$, and the connection among agents of G is shown in the figure 5, where different states are represented by the components P_h , $h = 1, 2, 3, 4$ of G . It is to be noted that $|P_1| > |P_2| > |P_3| > |P_4| \geq 2$. For the sake of simplicity of notations, we have symbolized the vertex $v_i \in V(G)$ by the index set i .

¹<https://networkx.org/>

Figure 5: Network system of the agents in different states, the agent v_i is symbolized by the index $i \forall i = 1, \dots, 32$ (a) represents component P_1 , (b) represents component P_2 , (c) represents component P_3 , (d) represents component P_4

The possible attack plans available to the hackers are $Y = \{Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, Y_4, Y_5\}$ whose attacking system has been described in the table III. Note that all the plans are not capable of attacking four states simultaneously. Some of them could only be capable of disrupting only two states while others are capable of attacking at least three sub-network. The table indicates which agents of G are directly impacted by the considered plan $Y_i \in Y$. With this given network configuration G , and possible attack plans Y , one can utilize the steps of Algorithm 1 to rank the available plans based on the overall benefits retrieved from respective agents with the suppressed mandatory requirement that the best plan could be capable of disrupting at least three states out of four available states.

Table III: Different attacking plans of the hackers

# Plan	Direct impacted agent of states
Y_1	{3, 10, 2, 5, 11, 4, 20, 16, 18, 19}
Y_2	{7, 10, 1, 8, 5, 6, 16, 17, 13, 15}
Y_3	{11, 4, 7, 1, 12, 10, 20, 16, 17, 14, 23, 22, 26, 31, 30, 28}
Y_4	{7, 9, 2, 3, 5, 1, 18, 20, 19, 17, 24, 25, 22}
Y_5	{8, 9, 7, 1, 12, 2, 19, 16, 18, 14, 23, 25, 27, 28, 31, 30}

First, we assign the weights w_i^h ($i = 1, \dots, 32$, $h = 1, \dots, 4$) to the agents based on the connectivity in the associated network system according to equations (21) and (22). For example, to assign weights to the agents of P_3 , we first find the number of distinct connected components when the agents is removed one by one from the sub-network P_3 . One may note that on removing any agent from the sub-network P_3 , except the agent 27, we still obtain the connected subgraph; while on removing the agent 27, we have two distinct sub-components of P_3 . Thus, we have $n_1 = 2$ and $n_2 = 1$ ($l = 2$ here). Therefore, $P_3^1 = \{27\}$ and $P_3^2 = \{21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26\}$. Utilizing,

equations (21) and (22), we get $w_{27}^3 = \frac{1}{2}$ and $w_i^3 = \frac{1}{12}$ $i \in P_3^2$. Similarly, we compute the weights of respective agents in other components. The information about weights of respective agents are shown in Table IV.

Given the computed assigned weight w_i^h for the particular agent $v_i^h \in P_h$ and a attack plan $Y_i \in Y$, we compute the benefit degree $g_Y(v_i^h)$ reaped by the hacker from the agent v_i^h by utilizing equation (23) and are summarized in Table IV.

Table IV: Weight and benefit degrees of the agents under different plans

# agent(v_i^h)	weight (w_i^h)	benefit degree from plans				
		$g_{Y_1}(v_i^h)$	$g_{Y_2}(v_i^h)$	$g_{Y_3}(v_i^h)$	$g_{Y_4}(v_i^h)$	$g_{Y_5}(v_i^h)$
1	0.03	0.00	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
2	0.03	0.08	0.00	0.08	0.08	0.08
3	0.03	0.08	0.00	0.08	0.08	0.00
4	0.03	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5	0.12	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.01
6	0.03	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00
7	0.03	0.00	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
8	0.50	0.01	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.09
9	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.08	0.08
10	0.12	0.08	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00
11	0.03	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
12	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08
13	0.05	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00
14	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13
15	0.05	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00
16	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.12
17	0.05	0.00	0.12	0.13	0.13	0.00
18	0.05	0.13	0.00	0.13	0.13	0.13
19	0.50	0.14	0.01	0.14	0.14	0.13
20	0.12	0.13	0.00	0.13	0.13	0.01
21	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
22	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.14	0.00
23	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
24	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.14	0.00
25	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.14	0.15
26	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
27	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.15
28	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20
29	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
30	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20
31	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20
32	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03

As the interconnection among the agents in the state is well described by the graph, one can utilize the proposed graph based BM operator, given in equation (24) to compute benefits from respective state by a particular plan from the individual benefit degrees of the agents. Specifically, from individual benefit degree $g_P(v_i^h)$ of each agents $v_i^h \in P_h$ against a plan $Y_i \in Y$, we calculate the accumulated benefit degree (p_h^Y) obtained by the respective states $P_h \forall h = 1, \dots, d$ by utilizing equation (24). The results are shown in Table V. Note that the value of the parameters p and q in equation (24) is taken as $p = q = 1$. Afterwards, we prioritize the states P_h ($h = 1, \dots, 4$) according to the number of agents in each state and compute the priority weights w_h^Y from the computed accumulated benefit degrees (p_h^Y) from respective states by using equation (25). The results are summarized in Table V.

One can observe from Table V that the accumulated benefit degree obtained from some of the plans against the states are zero due to their incapability of affecting sub-networks of the respective state. Next, we model the mandatory requirement of the decision system that the foremost plan must be capable of attacking at least three states out of the four available states. This mandatory requirement can be transferred into the framework of the aggregation process where we compute the final accumulated benefit degree retrieved from a plan by enforcing the condition that for achieving a non-zero aggregated benefit degree from a particular plan at least the conjunctions of individual benefit degrees from any three states must be at a non-zero level. This mandatory requirement could be modeled by setting up the parameter $k = 3$ in equation (26). Finally, the overall aggregated benefit degree f_G^{*Y} obtained by a plan Y is calculated by utilizing equation (26), the results are reported in Table V. One can observe from Table V that the accumulated benefit degree from plans Y_1 and Y_2 are zero for not satisfying the mandatory requirement. Based on the aggregated benefit degree $f_G^{*Y_i}$, ($i = 1, \dots, 4$), the available plans can be ranked as follows: $Y_5 \succ Y_3 \succ Y_4 \succ \{Y_2, Y_1\}$. It is evident that the attack plan Y_4 is more effective in damaging the network system of the targeted organization in the best possible way.

Table V: Aggregated Benefit degree from different states and plans

# Plan (Y_i)	accumulated benefit degree reaped from states (p_h^Y)				prioritize weights (w_h^Y)				aggregated benefit degree ($f_G^{*Y_i}$)
	$p_1^{Y_i}$	$p_2^{Y_i}$	$p_3^{Y_i}$	$p_4^{Y_i}$	$w_1^{Y_i}$	$w_2^{Y_i}$	$w_3^{Y_i}$	$w_4^{Y_i}$	
Y_1	0.030111	0.080218	0.0	0.0	1	0.030110	0.002415	0.0	0.0
Y_2	0.047399	0.059403	0.0	0.0	1	0.047399	0.002816	0.0	0.0
Y_3	0.044222	0.050855	0.054467	0.120830	1	0.044222	0.002249	0.000122	0.050742
Y_4	0.035402	0.083979	0.016330	0.0	1	0.035402	0.002973	0.000049	0.036267
Y_5	0.033533	0.073033	0.068139	0.120830	1	0.033533	0.002449	0.000167	0.056002

Although we have illustrated the working of our method with a hypothetical small-size network, in practice, it can work for any large-scale network system. It can also work for any network topology as long as the corresponding graph is simple. And the same is true for not only the hacker attack system but also in any practical aggregation system with such interconnected information sources.

Further, the above discussion shows that the proposed operators are well-competent in handling precise connections among data arguments. Also, the mandatory conditions of the decision system can be effectively imposed over the system as illustrated through the Hacker attack system. This approves that the proposed operator are adequate for modeling vivid real-life problems due to their flexibility in handling the convoluted network systems. In a nutshell, the hacker attack system example demonstrates how the interconnection among the information source in the form of a graph can be handled with the graph-based generalization of Bonferroni mean in the aggregation process, unlike the other variants of BM.

8. Conclusion

This study focuses on exploring a theoretical framework of a distinctive form of the BM operator that captures interrelationships among data entities portrayed through vivid graphical patterns. First of all, a mechanism

for characterizing association among different entities has been proposed. Then, different models of interrelationship structure among entities utilized in vivid real-world problems are handled through different patterns of graphs. A constructive methodology of an upgraded form of the BM operator, denoted by the f_G^{BM} operator has been proposed by formulating a mathematical framework that can effortlessly describe complex and dissimilar connections among data entities by using classical graphs. The knowledge of association information among different entities is encompassed into the processing system of the proposed f_G^{BM} operator in an exclusive manner that provides reliable accumulated information by precisely capturing exact association among entities. For improving the potentiality of the proposed f_G^{BM} operator, a generalized version of it has also been proposed by suitably replacing its sub-components with the other forms of conjunctive or averaging aggregation functions. The generalized form has been proposed in a distinctive manner such that the operator is able to accumulate the interaction information among entities depicted through graphs along with handling mandatory prerequisites that exist within the decision system. The prime advantage of proposing the generalized form of the f_G^{BM} operator is that the operator is able to handle certain mandatory conditions as desired by the considered systems along with capturing association among entities portrayed through graphs. Also, the generalized form makes accessible the users' wide range of representations of the f_G^{BM} operator by taking different mandatory conditions that ensure versatility of the operator to handle complex decision systems. The significant properties of the proposed generalized form can be obtained through the respective behavior of the operators utilized in its construction process, and are effortlessly manageable. For an application purpose, the proposed operator has been utilized over the decision-making problem of the Hacker attack system, where the hacker wishes to choose the best possible plan from all the available plans in a way that damages the network system of the organization as worst as possible.

Further extension in this line of research includes the proposition of an upgraded class of aggregation operators where the connective information among entities can be depicted through directed graphs. Such operators can be effectively utilized for handling non-symmetric association among the inputs, hence more flexible in capturing broad spectrum of interrelationship patterns. The mechanism of capturing interrelationships through graphs can be surpassed into the processing system of the Choquet integral operators, well utilized for handling interactive characteristics among the entities with support of fuzzy measures. Furthermore, the proposed operators are required to be remodeled in a way that they are able to uphold different requirements of the decision systems, like optional requirements, mandatory and sufficient requirements, etc. This study can be further extended to the concept of the pre-aggregation operators [36], [48] where one wishes to acquire monotonicity along a specified direction by its input arguments.

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